

1. 100% pollen sterility in F₂ Vytilla-3/IR36.

2. 92% pollen sterility in F₂ Vytilla-3/IR36.

From the segregation progenies of the cross Vytilla-3 × IR36, we were able to isolate four completely CMS lines suitable for warm, humid climatic conditions at Kerala (Figs. 1 and 2).

Virmani et al (1985) reported attaining a highly sterile BC₄F₁ progeny from the cross ARC13829-26/IR1079-2-3-1.

Reference

Virmani SS, Raj KG, Casal C, Dalmacio RD, Aurin PA. 1985. Rice genetics. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. 635 p. ■

Inheritance study of seedling elongation in rice

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The inheritance of seedling elongation in rice was studied in the cross IR42 (dwarf nonelongating)/Jalamagna (tall elongating) for two different ages of

seedlings (21 and 30 d old) under deep water conditions during the 1995 wet season at CRRI. Seedlings of F₁ and F₂ and parental lines raised in small galvanized iron trays (size 50 × 40 cm) were submerged in a water tank. Seedling heights were taken just before submergence. On the first day of submergence, water depth was 40 cm which was raised the following day to 80 cm and 90 cm for 21- and 30-d-old seedlings, respectively. These levels were maintained for 7 d.

Seedling heights were recorded after draining the tank. The mean heights of F₁ and the elongating parent (Jalamagna) before submergence with 21- and 30-d-old seedlings were 42 and 43 cm, and 48 and 47 cm, respectively (see figure). The respective values after submergence were 80 and 85 cm, and 122 and 126 cm, respectively, suggesting the dominance of elongation ability. The figure shows the frequency distribution curves for height. The segregation pattern for height observed in the F₂ before and after submergence is described below.

For 21 DAS, seedling height before submergence ranged from 20 to 70 cm

and plant distribution was distinctly unimodal, with a peak at 55 cm. After submergence, plant height ranged from 30 to 110 cm, separating the population into elongating type (such as Jalamagna) and nonelongating type (such as IR42); distribution was bimodal. Of 235 F₂ plants studied, 130 were elongating and 105 were non-elongating, fitting the 9:7 ratio ($\chi^2 = 0.0818, P = 0.75-0.90$).

For 30 DAS, seedling height varied from 20 to 75 cm before submergence. Plant distribution was unimodal. After submergence, distribution was clearly bimodal, with a wider height range of 40-150 cm. Of 244 F₂ plants, 148 were elongating types and 96 were non-elongating types, which fitted the 9:7 ratio ($\chi^2 = 1.924, P = 0.10-0.25$).

Results suggested two dominant complementary genes responsible for seedling elongation in rice. The presence of both genes conferred an elongation ability similar to that of Jalamagna, and the absence of either gene or both genes resulted in plants such as IR42, the nonelongating parent. ■

Frequency distribution of plant height (cm) in 21- and 30-d-old F₂ populations of IR42/Jalamagna. Horizontal lines show the range of height of parents and F₁s about the mean (solid circle).